

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN SCHOOL

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Abstract

This study is devoted to identifying the peculiarities of classroom management in learning English as a foreign language. The authors analyze the efficacy, principles, and approaches of classroom management systems. They also highlight problems encountered by students while learning English and provide learning strategies that help learners structure their thinking. Two types of motivation — extrinsic and intrinsic — are analyzed. The paper emphasizes teachers' struggles with classroom discipline and students' reluctance to prepare for the challenges they face. The results of the study demonstrate the need for time management skills and experienced instructional teachers. Teachers are expected to take the lead role in classroom management.

Keywords: classroom management, English, foreign language, teacher, students, school.

*I see and I forget.
I hear and I remember.
I do and I understand.
Confucius*

Introduction. One of the biggest challenges in the teaching profession is classroom management. Most of the coursework in teacher preparation programs is devoted to certification content, and very little covers classroom management. Such skills are often acquired only through experience. Today's students are quick to spot weaknesses in control or consistency, and a teacher without adequate classroom management skills may struggle to succeed.

All educators know that classroom management helps teachers build a classroom culture in which students are inspired to work hard, participate actively, achieve higher levels of success, and engage in productive activities. Classroom management refers to the strategies and practices employed by educators to create an organized, productive, and respectful learning environment. It encompasses a range of techniques, such as setting clear expectations and maintaining a structured routine [13].

The *purpose* of classroom management is important for:

- ✓ ensuring that classroom lessons run smoothly;
- ✓ linking to issues of motivation, discipline and respect;
- ✓ preventing disruptive behavior;
- ✓ involving clear communication of academic expectations;
- ✓ creating a cooperative learning environment.

Effective classroom-management systems work best when three basic *principles* are embedded [2, 39-40]:

1. Emphasize student expectations for learning rather than focusing only on problematic behavior and discipline issues.

2. Support the learning environment by promoting active learning and student involvement, not merely compliance with rules.

3. Identify for students the behaviors integral to the instructional agenda.

Effective classroom management also requires a comprehensive approach that includes the following [8]:

- ✓ structuring the classroom environment;
- ✓ actively supervising student enrolment;
- ✓ implementing classroom rules and routines;
- ✓ enacting procedures that encourage appropriate learning behaviour;
- ✓ using behaviour reduction strategies;
- ✓ collecting and using evidences to monitor student behaviour;
- ✓ modifying classroom management procedures as needed.

Moreover, integrating data-driven decision-making into classroom management practices can greatly enhance their effectiveness. Data-driven decision-making involves systematically collecting, analyzing, and interpreting evidence — such as formative assessments, participation logs, attendance records, and student feedback — to inform pedagogical adjustments and interventions. By examining these data points, teachers can identify patterns of student engagement, pinpoint areas of difficulty, and tailor their instruction to meet learners' needs. Such an evidence-based approach aligns closely with efforts to refine teacher preparation and professional development [8], supports continuous improvement in instruction [5], and complements the use of self-regulated learning strategies [1,

4]. In essence, data-driven adjustments enable teachers to respond more effectively to students' varying proficiency levels, motivational states, and cultural backgrounds, ensuring a more inclusive and adaptive learning environment.

Results and discussions.

The planning continuum. Teachers of English as a foreign or second language are often concerned about having students at different proficiency levels. It is rare for two students to have exactly the same knowledge of English at any one time. The students' proficiency level frequently affects their motivation. For example, beginners who struggle with understanding and producing language may fail to progress, resulting in a relatively high drop-out rate. Intermediate students sometimes suffer from the so-called "plateau effect," finding it difficult to see progress from one week to the next, which can be demotivating.

Motivation is significantly influenced by students' goals. One of the strongest external motivators is the perceived purpose of learning English. Outside factors, such as the need to pass an exam, hopes for financial reward, or the possibility of future travel, drive extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation, on the other hand, comes from within the individual — enjoyment of the learning process or a desire for self-improvement [9].

Extrinsic Motivation

- **Teacher's Support in Organizing Students' Activities:** A supportive teacher who creates a positive and engaging learning environment can greatly influence students' motivation. Enthusiasm, constructive feedback, and encouragement foster a sense of achievement.

- **Initiating Student Activities:** Students need to know how much time they have for an activity and exactly when to start.

- **Workload and Assessment:** Assignments and grading should be balanced. Excessive pressure can decrease motivation, while reasonable workloads enhance the learning experience.

- **Recognition and Rewards:** Certificates, praise, or opportunities for practical application can serve as extrinsic motivators, giving students a sense of success and encouraging continued effort.

- **Respecting Students:** Creating a respectful environment fosters trust. Teachers should respond thoughtfully, listen attentively, respect cultural differences, maintain equitable practices, and avoid inflammatory language or raised voices.

Intrinsic Motivation

- **Interest in the Target Culture:** Students genuinely interested in English-speaking cultures — literature, music, art, cuisine — tend to show intrinsic motivation.

- **Home-School Partnerships:** Collaboration between families and schools can support learning and behavior. Meeting students' needs often improves their intrinsic drive.

- **Passion for Traveling:** Students who plan to visit English-speaking countries or interact with English speakers abroad see language skills as essential, motivating them intrinsically.

- **Bilingual Background:** Students who already speak another language or grew up in English-speaking environments often find learning English more familiar and less intimidating, boosting intrinsic motivation.

Outside the classroom, societal attitudes toward English learning also matter. If students choose between languages, cultural images associated with English — positive or negative — influence their motivation and engagement. These attitudes shape the student's commitment and the continuity of their motivation.

For successful communication, teachers must ensure participants "play by the same rules" [12, p. 17]. Cooperation involves making contributions that are informative, true, relevant, and clear, avoiding obscurity.

Thus, for example, if student *A* asks a question, he or she expects student *B* to give an answer. That means cooperation which states that speakers should (1) make their contribution as informative as required, (2) make their contribution true, (3) make their contribution relevant, and (4) avoid obscurity — and be brief orderly.

Mixed-ability classes pose challenges in lesson planning. Nevertheless, most teachers think about what they will teach before class. Tessa Woodward notes that teachers always do some preparation [14, p. 25].

Jim Scrivener, on the other hand, describes a situation where the teacher has no real idea what he or she is going to do before a lesson starts and where as a result the lesson is created moment by moment with the teacher and the learners working with whatever is happening in the classroom. He calls it a 'jungle path' lesson. He gives an example of the teacher walking into a classroom and asking *How was the weekend?* and after listening to a number of answers, provoking a discussion based on what has been said. At some point the teacher may then select particular items of language that have emerged and invent instant exercises that will help students work on them [9, 132].

Anyone who speaks English fluently and who is reasonably inventive, friendly, firm, and patient should make a fine conversation leader. A person with these qualities need to a professional teacher because he enjoys helping speakers use English. Certainly an enthusiastic attitude is essential. A spirit of inventiveness is also important, so the teacher can maintain the lively continuity with students [6].

The next question to be answered is to view the teacher's role with a group of students in terms of differentiation. Differentiation allows teachers to provide tasks suited to students' varied abilities and interests. It can mean giving different texts to read, responding to students differently, or grouping them by ability. This helps the teacher gauge the class's mood, understand overall progress, and refine instruction.

Effective classroom management plays a crucial role in creating an ideal learning environment. It encompasses various components, including establishing rules and expectations, managing student behavior, and fostering an atmosphere conducive to learning. In the context of teaching English as a foreign language, classroom management requires additional considerations due to the specific linguistic and cultural challenges involved. Classroom management plays a huge

role in facilitating effective teaching and learning in any educational setting, including foreign language classrooms. It involves creating a conducive environment that promotes academic and social-emotional learning, as well as maximizing instructional time. Effective classroom management techniques not only benefit students academically, but also foster positive social opportunities and contribute to a positive classroom atmosphere [11].

Additionally, classroom management is especially important for foreign language teachers as it can impact their job satisfaction and the overall success of language learning. In the context of learning English as a foreign language, classroom management becomes even more significant. One aspect of classroom management is establishing clear expectations regarding language use. In the case of learning English, it is essential to create an immersive environment where students are encouraged to communicate primarily in English. This can be achieved through *strategies* such as using target language labels, setting language use goals, and providing opportunities for authentic communication. Another crucial component of classroom management is addressing individual learning needs. As students come from diverse backgrounds, they may have varying levels of prior exposure to English.

One of the most important tasks that teachers have to perform is that of organising students to do various activities. This often involves giving the students information, telling them how they are going to do the activity, putting them into pairs/groups and finally closing things down when it is time to stop.

The first thing teachers need to do when organising something is to provide clear, logical *instructions*, possibly supported by demonstrations, ensure students understand what is expected of them. Here it is important to get the level of the language right and try to present instructions in a logical order and in as unconfusing a way as possible [7]. It is frequently a good idea to get students to give the instructions back, in English or in their own language as a check on whether they have understood them. An important tool in instruction is for the teacher to organise a demonstration of what is to happen. If students are going to use a chart or table to ask other students questions and record their answers, for example, getting a student up to the front to demonstrate the activity with you may be worth any answer of complex instructions. Demonstration is almost always appropriate and will almost always ensure that students have a better grasp of what they are supposed to do than instructions can on their own.

So, teachers have to employ differentiated instruction techniques to accommodate the needs of all learners and provide additional support to those who require it. This can involve incorporating various instructional materials, such as textbooks and reference books, digital resources, audiovisual materials, authentic texts, worksheets/workbooks, educational language games and simulations, charts/graphs/diagrams, case studies and real-world examples to engage students at different proficiency levels.

Moreover, foreign language teaching involves distinct characteristics that influence classroom management. Effective instruction requires the use of a language that students do not yet understand, necessitates interaction patterns, and employs diverse, student-focused teaching methodologies [3]. These features affect how teachers manage their classrooms and create specific challenges related to students' language proficiency and self-esteem, as well as the need for clear rules and guidelines to control negative class participation. Understanding these distinctive characteristics is crucial for foreign language teachers to navigate classroom management effectively. The evolution of teaching approaches in foreign language education has seen a shift from grammar-based methodologies to more communicative approaches. Grammar-based methods emphasize grammar rules, translation, and deductive teaching, while communicative approaches focus on learning to communicate and achieving communicative competence through interaction. These changes in teaching methods impact classroom management by influencing student-teacher interactions, participation, and the use of the target language.

The day-to-day focus of schools has always been on learning – how to know, how to know more efficiently and how to know more effectively. The philosophy is more about what students are now ready to learn, how their learning can be enabled, and increasing the 'how to learn' proficiencies of students. In this scenario, the purpose of schooling is to equip students with learning strategies, or the skills of learning how to learn. Of course, learning and achievement are not dichotomous; they are related [10]. Through growth in learning in specific domains comes achievement and from achievement there can be much learning.

Learning strategies help the learner structure his/her thinking so as to plan, set goals and monitor progress, make adjustments and evaluate the process of learning and the outcomes. These strategies can be categorised in many ways according to various domains and classifications. Boekaerts, for example, argued for three *types of learning strategies*: 1) Cognitive strategies such as elaboration, to deepen the understanding of the domain studied; 2) Metecognitive strategies such as planning, to regulate the learning process; 3) Motivational strategies such as self-efficacy, to motivate oneself to engage in learning [1].

Given the advent of newer ways to access information now students' fingerprints, it is appropriate that Dignath, Buettner and Langfeldt added a fourth category – management strategies such as finding, navigating, and evaluating [4].

Conclusion. Classroom management remains one of the greatest challenges in teaching. Such skills are typically acquired through experience. Good management ensures that lessons run smoothly, discipline is maintained, and diverse learners are accommodated. This concept is crucial in addressing various challenges that teachers face with, especially in the initial years of teaching, such as classroom discipline, dealing with individual differences, organization of class work, relationships with parents, insufficient teaching materials, and overcrowded classrooms.

Not having yet acquired the necessary skills to thrive in the classroom (such as time management, classroom management, and instructional experience) can put a teacher at a distinct disadvantage.

Teachers' knowledge involves knowing the personal, relational, and cultural standards of students' competences, skills, interests of their communication. So, without any doubt, motivation plays a vital role in language learning. It can be assumed that for students with a weak level of motivation, it is a need to strengthen the active role of the teacher. With motivated learners, learning a foreign language becomes effective, immersive, and enjoyable.

Teachers themselves can play a crucial role in conducting research on classroom management issues in their own classrooms, enhancing their professional development and encourage students into participation in the network-based international language learning projects accomplished in collaboration with the students from a variety of cultures using the same foreign language.

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